

**Fashion's methane footprint:
Estimated
emissions
intensity and
importance
across the
global industry**

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Abstract:

Methane is a potent greenhouse gas (GHG) with a global warming potential (GWP) 27 times higher than that of CO₂ over a 100-year period, and 86 times higher over a 20-year period, yet it receives little attention in the fashion industry which is a significant contributor to global GHG emissions. This study provides a comprehensive estimate of methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry by using a cradle-to-grave approach to calculate impacts from raw material extraction to finished goods. Using a systematic literature review and a life cycle inventory (LCI), our findings estimate the fashion industry is responsible for approximately 8.3 million tonnes of CH₄/year (223.39 million tonnes CO₂ eq CH₄/year). Animal-derived materials (leather, wool, and cashmere) even in their raw form, prove to be the largest sources of methane among the examined categories, accounting for about 75% of total emissions. Raw material processing and fiber processing, particularly cotton processing, represent the second highest contributor to methane emissions at about 12% of total emissions. To the authors' knowledge, this study is the first of its kind to estimate the methane emissions associated with the fashion industry.

1. Introduction:

The fashion industry is increasingly scrutinized for its environmental impact, and is estimated to be responsible for as much as 10% of global GHG emissions (Niinimäki et al., 2020). The fashion industry's relationship with climate change is often discussed in terms of kg CO₂ eq which can lead to simplifications of the complex contributing factors at play. Methane (CH₄) is a potent greenhouse gas with about 27 times the warming power of CO₂ over a 100-year time period. CO₂ remains in the atmosphere for centuries, but methane's atmospheric lifetime is relatively short at about 12 years (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2021). However, during this period, it traps heat far more effectively than CO₂, with a global warming potential (GWP) even 86 times higher over a 20-year timeframe (Environmental Defense Fund, 2022). This intensity makes methane reduction particularly valuable for achieving essential and near-term climate goals in the fashion industry, with potentially significant climate benefits resulting from fiber and textile swaps.

Methane is a well-known output of agricultural systems for food, but it also represents a portion of fashion's climate impact, arising from various stages of textile production from the cultivation and extraction of raw materials, the dyeing and spinning of fibers, garment assembly, and landfilling. This impact stems primarily from the industry's reliance on animal-derived materials such as wool and leather. About 56% of bovine farming GHG emissions (in terms of CO₂ eq), the sources of cow skins, are attributed to methane (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2024). Similarly, up to 90% of GHG emissions from ovine farming in wool and meat production are attributed to methane (Biswas et al., 2010). Cattle farming alone makes up about 8% of global anthropogenic GHG emissions (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2024). Even as a co-product of the meat and dairy industries, significant emissions are allocated to the production of cow skins based on factors like biophysical and economic value (De Rosa-Giglio P. et al., 2018). Most synthetic fibers, like polyester, are derived from fossil fuels, and their upstream supply chains contribute to methane emissions. In oil extraction regions such as the Permian Basin, methane leakage can reach approximately 9.63% of gas extracted, making fossil-based textile feedstocks a non-trivial source of methane emissions (Bianchi et al., 2023; Sherwin et al., 2024).

2. Methodology

2.1 Systematic Literature Review

A PRISMA method systematic review was conducted using Web of Science and Google Scholar to identify methane emissions values within a cradle-to-grave framework assuming all materials will be landfilled at the end of life. Global material production volumes associated with apparel and footwear were gathered from the Textile Exchange 2024 Materials Market Report. Search terms for impact included "methane emissions," "carbon footprint," and "global warming potential". Material categories were identified with the terms: wool, cashmere, leather, polyester, polyurethane, polypropylene, nylon, cotton, hemp, and viscose. Manufacturing processes were identified with the terms: tanning, spinning, weaving, extrude, dyeing, knitting, factory, and manufacturing. Studies were selected based on their explicit reporting of methane emissions. A total of 21,377 peer-reviewed articles were initially identified for all materials and processes examined, with 274 papers retrieved for full-text review, and 16 papers included for explicit methane emission values in fiber production. Additional data was extracted from white papers. In cases of materials or processes missing entirely from the literature, those materials and processes were omitted from the following literature methodology sections.

Wool Literature

1,980 kton of greasy wool, resulting in 1,060 kton of clean wool, was produced in 2023. About 70%, 742 kton was used for apparel (Textile Exchange, 2025). The literature reports a range of CH₄ representing up to 90% of wool emissions, so we apply a value of 88% to the median value of 26.82 kg CO₂ eq of CH₄/kg greasy wool calculated as the average of the methane emissions values reported in 9 articles (Alcock et al., 2015; Brock et al., 2013; Cottle and Cowie, 2016; Dougherty, 2018; Eady et al., 2012; Bianco et al., 2023; Biswas et al., 2010; Browne et al., 2011; Li et al., 2024).

Leather Literature

Using the UNIDO PCR GHG emissions value of 101.087 kg CO₂ eq/kg finished leather (excluding tanning) and applying a methane proportion of 56% to that GHG value, we estimate 56.61 kg CO₂ eq CH₄/kg leather. Considering 13.4 million tonnes raw hides were produced in 2022 (FAOa, 2022), 60-85% of leather is used for apparel, footwear, and accessories (73% applied here) (Textile Exchange, 2025), and 4.6 kg cow skin/1 kg finished leather ratio (Kılıç et al., 2023), we estimate the global leather footprint at 4.47 million tonnes CH₄/year, with 9.26 kton CH₄ associated with all leather tanning operations (Joseph & Nithya, 2008).

Polypropylene Literature

The literature reports a value of 12 g CH₄/kg resin (Muthu, 2020). Approximately 6,200 kton of polypropylene fiber were produced in 2022, of which we assume 50% is used for apparel (Textile Exchange, 2025).

Polyamide (Nylon) Literature

Nylon 6 and Nylon 66 production emits between 47–49 g CH₄ per kg (Muthu, 2020). Averaging to 48 g CH₄/kg (0.048 kg CH₄/kg), we apply this emissions rate to an estimated 6,700 kton of global nylon fiber output in 2022. Assuming 50% of nylon production is used in apparel (Textile Exchange, 2025), we attribute 3,350 kton of nylon fiber to apparel.

Cotton Literature

The literature reports a value of 7.6 g CH₄/kg raw cotton (Kalliala and Nousiainen, 1999). The 2023 global cotton production is approximately 24,400 kton, with an estimated 70% for apparel (Textile Exchange, 2025).

Hemp Literature

The literature reports 0.198 g CH₄/kg hemp (Muthu, 2020). With an estimated 200 kton of hemp fiber produced globally in 2023, and the majority of this volume used for non-apparel applications (Textile Exchange, 2025), we estimate <40 tonnes CH₄/year attributable to hemp fiber production.

2.2 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The systematic literature review revealed gaps in quantitative reporting of methane emissions for multiple materials and processes in the fashion industry. To fill the literature gaps, a life cycle inventory for each material type and process considered in the study was produced using SimaPro, a leading LCA software. Where possible, exact processes from cradle-to-grave were applied. If the exact process was not available in the data library, a similar process was applied. The analysis focuses exclusively on emissions to air, specifically volume of methane, including “methane”, “methane, biogenic”, and “methane, land transformation” using the TRACI 2.1 method.

Wool LCI

In SimaPro, datasets for sheep fleece and knitting were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 1,386 kton and 742 kton respectively. Datasets for bleaching and dyeing yarn, electricity, and landfilling were applied in Processes with 742 kton, 558,2040 MWh, and 742 kton respectively. Though many datasets for wool processing were not available, a value of 7.71 MWh/ton clean wool was assumed based on the literature.

Cashmere LCI

25.611 kton of greasy cashmere, resulting in about 12.805 kton of clean cashmere, was produced in 2023. No direct reports of methane emissions associated from cashmere exist in the literature to the authors' knowledge. In SimaPro, datasets for sheep fleece and knitting were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 358.554 kton and 12.805 kton respectively. Datasets for bleaching and dyeing yarn, electricity, and landfilling were applied in Processes with 12.805 kton, 98,730 MWh, and 12.805 kton respectively. As cashmere is not available in the data library, a factor of .7 for animal size was applied to the wool data, and a factor of 20 was applied for fiber yield per animal (FAOb, 2022) at the raw material level. Though datasets for cashmere processing were not available, a value of 7.71 MWh/ton clean cashmere was assumed based on the wool literature.

Polyester LCI

70,700 kton of polyester was produced in 2023 with about 60%, 42,420 kton, used for apparel. No direct reports of methane emissions associated with polyester fibers or textiles exist in the literature to the authors' knowledge. In SimaPro, datasets for amorphous PET and polyester fiber spinning were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 42,420 kton for both. Datasets for synthetic fiber weaving and landfilling were applied in Processes with 42,420 kton for both.

Polypropylene LCI

6,200 kton of polypropylene was produced in 2023 with about 50%, 3,100 kton, used for apparel. In SimaPro datasets for LLDPE polyethylene granulate and nonwoven polypropylene textile production were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 3,100 kton for both. Landfilling was applied in Processes with 3,100 kton. Polypropylene was not available as a raw material dataset, so a similar dataset was applied.

Polyamide (Nylon) LCI

6,700 kton of nylon were produced in 2023 with about 50%, 3,350 kton, used for apparel. In SimaPro datasets for Polyamide (Nylon) 6.6, Polyamide (Nylon) 6, polyester fiber production, and textile weaving were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 1,675 kton, 1,675 kton, 3,350 kton, and 3,350 kton respectively. Landfilling was applied in Processes with 3,350 kton. A 50-50 split of nylon 6 and nylon 6.6 was applied across nylon production.

Cotton LCI

24,400 kton of cotton was produced in 2023 with about 70%, 17,080 kton, used for apparel. In SimaPro, datasets for organic Seed-cotton production, cotton fiber ginning, cotton yarn production, and cotton textile knitting were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 17,080 kton for all. Datasets for cotton fiber dyeing, woven cotton textile finishing, and landfilling were applied in Processes with 17,080 kton for all.

Viscose LCI

7,900 kton of viscose was produced in 2023 with about 80% of the fibers, 6,320 kton, used for apparel. In SimaPro, datasets for viscose fiber spinning and bleached sulfite pulp were applied in Materials/Assemblies with 6,320 kton and 15,800 kton respectively. Datasets for fiber dyeing, fiber weaving, and landfilling were applied in Processes with 6,320 kton for all three. A 1 kg viscose fiber/2.5 kg pulp is assumed.

Polyurethane LCI

No direct reporting of methane from polyurethane (PU) methane were identified in the literature. About 35.8 kton of polyurethane was used in apparel and footwear. In SimaPro, the dataset for Polyurethane flexible foam E was applied in Materials/Assemblies with 35.8 kton. Landfilling was applied in Processes with 35.8 kton.

3. Meta-Analysis Results

Our methodology follows a cradle-to-grave framework, measuring emissions from the extraction of raw materials through the end of life assuming all products will be landfilled. Emissions values were extracted from literature where available and supplemented by LCI data where necessary. Global material production volumes associated with apparel were gathered from the Textile Exchange 2024 Materials Market Report. Each value across the materials' lifecycles are extracted from reports and datasets which cover a mix of geographic regions.

Wool

We consider 1,372 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction according to the literature. We also consider 19.83 kton CH₄/yr from processing, 21.26 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication, and .007 kton CH₄/yr for landfilling according to LCI data. We estimate that wool contributes approximately 1,413.1 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Cashmere

We consider 355.18 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction according to weighted wool literature data, .26 kton CH₄/yr from processing according to weighted wool LCI data, .37 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication and .0001 kton CH₄/yr from landfilling according to LCI data. We estimate that cashmere contributes approximately 355.81 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Cotton

We consider 59.68 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction according to LCI data. We also consider 850.72 kton CH₄/yr from processing, 501.01 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication, and .15 kton CH₄/yr from landfilling according to LCI data. We estimate that cotton contributes approximately 1,411.57 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Polypropylene

We consider 37.2 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction according to the literature. We also consider 73.75 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication and .027 kton CH₄/yr for landfilling according to LCI data. We estimate that polypropylene contributes approximately 110.97

Polyester

We consider 78.2 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction, 1 kton CH₄/yr from processing, 8.78 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication, and .04 kton CH₄/yr from landfilling, all according to LCI data. We estimate that polyester contributes approximately 88.02 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Polyurethane

We consider 1.17 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction and less than 2 g CH₄/yr from landfilling according to LCI data. We estimate that polyurethane contributes approximately 1.17 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Viscose

We consider 48.02 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction, 85.46 kton CH₄/yr from processing, 13.22 kton CH₄/yr from fabrication, and .07 kton CH₄/yr from landfilling, all according to LCI data. We estimate that viscose contributes approximately 146.76 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Leather

We consider 4,465.76 kton CH₄/yr from raw material extraction and 9.26 kton CH₄/yr from processing according to the literature. We estimate that leather contributes approximately 4,475 kton CH₄/yr to the methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry.

Material	Methane from Raw Material (kton/yr)	Methane from Processing (kton/yr)	Methane from Fabrication (kton/yr)	Methane from Landfilling (kton/yr)	Total (kton/yr)
Wool	1372	19.8293387	21.260608	0.0074517439	1,413.097398
Cashmere	355.18	0.259052338	0.3750107	0.000131914777	355.814195
Cotton	59.680438	850.724352	501.0143	0.146204919	1411.565295
Polypropylene	37.2	-	73.74611	0.02664	110.97275
Nylon	160.8	-	110.60911	0.02874018	271.4378502
Polyester	78.2	1.00251	8.7800653	0.036300228	88.01887553
Polyurethane	1.17	-	-	0.00000000193	1.170000002
Viscose	48.01524	85.455536	13.2200973	0.065051383	146.7559247
Leather	4,465.76	9.260869565	-	-	4,475.02
SUM	6,578.003678	966.5316586	729.0053013	0.3105203706	8,273.851158

Table 1. Yearly methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry calculated LCA software modeling and literature review. Values highlighted in yellow were generated in the software, and the remaining values were gathered from the literature. Empty cells represent values that could not be reasonably found or separated out from LCA software or literature. Each value across the materials' lifecycles are extracted from reports and datasets which cover a mix of geographic regions.

4. Discussion

Animal-derived leather and wool, despite representing a smaller fraction of total textile production volume compared to synthetic or plant-based fibers, have an outsized impact on methane emissions due to the biological nature of ruminant digestion, which produces methane through enteric fermentation. Unlike other materials where methane emissions stem primarily from electricity use in processing and goods manufacturing reliant on fossil fuels and coal energy sources, emissions from wool and leather originate from the animals themselves, making methane reductions inherently more challenging without shifts away from these materials. Leather production alone accounts for approximately 50% of total methane emissions in the global fashion industry. This is largely due to the cattle industry's significant contribution to global methane emissions, where 56% of bovine-related GHG emissions are from methane (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2024). Similarly, clean wool contributes an additional 1,392 kton CH₄ annually, driven by enteric fermentation from sheep, which account for up to 90% of wool's total emissions (Biswas et al., 2010). Combined, these two materials contribute nearly 71% of the methane footprint of fashion, despite constituting a much smaller share of total fiber and material production volume, about 4%.

Fig. 1. Estimated total methane emissions volume associated with the fashion industry per year (kton CH₄/yr), based on aggregated life cycle inventories of raw material procurement, processing stage, and end-of-life landfilling. Synthetic fibers (polyester, nylon, polypropylene, and polyurethane) are grouped as "Synthetics". "Textile Fabrication" considers the weaving and knitting of materials included in this study. Percentages indicate the relative contribution of each portion to total methane emissions from fashion supply chains.

Annual fashion materials production volume

Fig. 2. Estimated distribution of annual production volume of major fashion materials used globally. Volumes are expressed in kilotonnes per year (kton material/yr), representing the approximate scale of fiber production entering the fashion supply chain based on the Textile Exchange Market Report. Synthetic fibers (polyester, nylon, polypropylene, and polyurethane) are grouped as “Synthetics”. Percentages indicate the proportion of each material relative to the total global production of fashion materials.

Polyester, the most abundant material in the fashion industry in terms of mass (over 42 million tons/yr), demonstrates the 7th lowest methane emissions across its lifetime out of 9 materials included in the study, with about 79 kton CH₄/yr. Viscose, though it makes up less than 9% of the mass of the materials evaluated in this study, contributes approximately 133 kton CH₄/yr, nearly twice that of polyester.

Yearly global methane emissions: fashion materials

Fig. 3. Estimated annual methane emissions associated with major fashion apparel materials, expressed in kilotonnes per year (kton CH₄/yr). Bars are segmented to indicate contributions from raw material production (e.g., farmed animal rearing or fiber cultivation) through processing (e.g., spinning, bleaching, dyeing), and end-of-life landfilling. “Textile Fabrication” considers the weaving and knitting of materials included in this study.

Raw materials procured from animal farming are the largest contributor to fashion's overall methane emissions at over 6,000 kton CH₄/yr. Leather (cow skin) methane emissions represent the largest volume from any single raw material category at about 4,466 kton CH₄/yr, and sheep's wool as the second largest contributor at about 1,370 kton CH₄/yr. Emissions intensity varies dramatically by material (Figure 4), with leather exhibiting an estimated methane emissions intensity of about 57 kg CO₂ eq CH₄/kg finished leather and wool about 50 kg CO₂ eq CH₄/kg clean wool. Even when considering processing and end-of-life phases, the emissions intensities of polyester, nylon, and cotton remain orders of magnitude lower. Fibers procured from plant sources, such as cotton and viscose, demonstrate low methane emissions at the raw material stage with about 60 kton CH₄/yr and 48 kton CH₄/yr respectively. Cotton and viscose are the only materials included in this study which are estimated to contribute more methane emissions in processing and post-processing phases than during raw material extraction with 1,350 kton CH₄/yr and 98 kton CH₄/yr respectively. Polyester exhibits a substantially lower methane footprint compared to animal-derived materials primarily because its production does not involve enteric fermentation. However, its widespread use causes other long-term environmental challenges due to its reliance on non-renewable hydrocarbons and its persistence in the ecosystems. Polyester fibers can remain intact in soils and marine environments for centuries (Henry et al., 2019; Geyer et al., 2017). While cotton represents a promising alternative, this analysis (and previous studies) shows that cotton fiber processing stages (including ginning, spinning, dyeing, and finishing) can be highly energy intensive, contributing to the material's overall methane and carbon footprint (Kalliala & Nousiainen, 1999; Hasanbeigi & Price, 2015). Creating viscose fibers involves breaking down cellulose with sodium hydroxide and carbon disulfide to spin it into fiber, which can harm workers and surrounding ecosystems and consumes large amounts of electricity (Shen et al., 2010). Processes for all fashion materials considered in this study including spinning, drying, weaving, knitting, dyeing, and finishing contribute approximately 1,695 kton CH₄/per year, a minor portion overall compared to raw material procurement which contributes approximately 6,578 kton CH₄/yr.

The landfilling of textiles also results in methane emissions, though seemingly far fewer than associated with landfilling more broadly, including that associated with food waste (Krause, 2018). We estimate that landfilling contributes only .31 kton CH₄/yr. Methane capture systems in modern landfills demonstrate the potential to lower this end-of-life estimate significantly, but vary greatly across sites. We apply the assumption that all fashion products will ultimately be landfilled as the fashion industry has not demonstrated capacity for large-scale textile recycling (Wójcik-Karpacz, A. et al., 2023). Most effectively, minimising the amount of textiles sent to landfill will reduce landfill emissions.

Methane intensity per kg of material

Fig. 4. Estimated methane emissions intensity per kilogram of material, expressed in kilograms of CO₂ equivalent methane per kilogram of finished material (kg CO₂ eq CH₄/kg material). Bars indicate life cycle methane emissions intensities for each material type, including raw material extraction, processing, and end-of-life landfilling.

Little work has been done to date on the GHG emissions associated with cashmere. In our estimate, we apply a factor for body size and a factor for fiber yield to the emissions associated with wool in order to build a new estimate for cashmere. Further work must be done on this material and the allocations for the associated emissions, but our estimate produces a methane intensity of approximately 14X that of wool due to extremely low fiber yield per animal, leading to an estimated intensity of about 750 kg CH₄/kg clean cashmere.

Methane mass and CO₂ eq impact

Fig. 5. Estimated climate impact of methane emissions associated with the global fashion industry. Each bar visualizes the conversion of methane mass to CO₂ eq emissions using two global warming potential (GWP) time horizons. The lower bar represents the unweighted methane mass (8,274 kton CH₄/yr). The middle and upper bars show the corresponding CO₂ eq impact applying GWP100 (factor of 27) and GWP20 (factor of 86), respectively. Each block corresponds to 8.4 Mt CH₄ mass.

Given the high global warming potential of methane over a 20-year time horizon (Figure 5), reducing methane emissions is critical for achieving near-term climate targets. This study's estimate 8.3 million tonnes of CH₄ annually attributed to the global fashion industry, equivalent to nearly 712 million tonnes of CO₂ eq CH₄ over 20 years, underscores that even modest reductions of methane emissions could have a measurable climate benefit. The fashion industry therefore has both the opportunity and responsibility to incorporate methane-focused interventions into its decarbonization commitments.

Little data is published on methane-specific emissions for fashion materials and industry activities. Limitations beyond the absence of peer-reviewed reported emissions values include low visibility across the fashion supply chain, making difficult to capture all contributing factors. For example, some materials including silk, rubber, metals, fur and wild animal skins are out of the scope of this study, as well as processes such as warehouse management, shoe and accessories construction operations, and washing which could contribute to the industry's overall emissions. Transportation is out of the scope of this study and is likely to contribute a comparatively marginal share of overall methane emissions, similar to other global supply chains (Liu et al. 2020). "Leather" in this study is assumed to be all cow-derived, though some skins in the fashion industry are also sourced from sheep, goats, and other species which may cause minimal variation in methane emissions levels based on allocation for co-products, diet, and other attributes which might lower or increase methane levels per skin. Alpaca wool and mohair, two fibers likely to have a high methane footprint due to their ruminant origins, are also out of the scope of this study due to limited data and use. Lyocell, and other man-made cellulosic fibers (MMCF) other than viscose, are out of the scope of this study. Garment- and brand-specific data on finished good construction (i.e. cutting and stitching) are out of the scope of this study due to lack of literature and library data. Finished good construction contributes about 8% of CO₂ eq emissions in the overall garment lifecycle from cradle to gate (Apparel Impact Institute, 2023), though it may contribute to overall methane emissions due to use of coal power for electricity in popular manufacturing regions. Regional variability in energy mix and farming practices are out of the scope of this study, as well as some variability in processes for transforming raw materials. Processes may vary between factories and finished product SKUs, and this study considers only the basic processes available for each material type in the LCA software used.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a first estimate of methane emissions from the fashion industry, revealing its significant climate impact. Our findings indicate that methane emissions from the fashion industry total at least 8.3 million tonnes CH₄ per year, equivalent to 223.39 million tonnes CO₂ eq CH₄/year. Considering the energy required for garment construction, the methane emissions data for which is not currently available in the literature, this footprint is likely to be even higher. The UN Environment Programme and The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) identify methane reduction as one of the most effective strategies for limiting near-term temperature rise, stating that methane emissions must be reduced by one third compared to 2020 levels, emphasizing the need for the fashion industry to address its methane footprint as part of any comprehensive climate strategy (IPCC, 2022; UNEP, 2022). Addressing methane emissions requires prioritizing reductions in ruminant animal-based leather and wool usage, as these two materials account for the majority of the industry's methane impact. Material swaps, such as replacing bovine leather with bio-based, fossil-free or recycled material alternatives and reducing reliance on virgin wool in favor of lower-impact recycled and plant-based fibers, could dramatically decrease methane emissions. The significant amount of methane associated with fabrication, as well as in the processing of cotton, must also be addressed.

To the authors' best knowledge, this estimate is the first of its kind to estimate the methane emissions associated with the fashion industry. Future research should refine methane estimates related to the fashion industry with a broader scope of materials including silk, rubber, metals, and exotic animal skins, mohair, alpaca wool, lyocell, as well as supply chain processes such as transport, garment construction, warehousing, and washing. This will be made possible by the continued development of product-specific LCAs which explicitly report methane values separate from overall GHG emissions. In collaboration with apparel companies with material usage and product assembly data, robust estimates can be developed for product-specific methane emissions and variability across seasonal collections.

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